

Hybrid SDN-Based Data-Centric Mobile Core Network with Content-Based Routing

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Abstract

The evolution of 6G core network architecture is a critical research area requiring comprehensive investigation and collaborative efforts. While multiple divergent visions exist, there is a consensus that 6G should be built on 5G achievements, such as softwarization, Service-Based Architecture (SBA), or network slicing, to ensure economic sustainability and foster innovation. Yet, most of the 6G architectural visions are revolutionary, raising questions about their feasibility in terms of financial sustainability and practical deployment. This paper introduces a Hybrid SDN-based Data-Centric Core Network (HSDCN) architecture combining multi-controller Software-Defined Networking (SDN), data-centric principles, and content-based routing to enable an optimized core network in cloud-native environments and facilitate the evolution of 5G networks towards 6G. HSDCN is a hybrid mobile network architecture, supporting low-latency Control Plane (CP) operations and facilitating AI-driven network operations while maintaining compatibility with 3GPP standards and avoiding disruptive design shifts.

Index Terms

6G, data-centric, core network, multi-controller SDN, content-based routing, AI

I. INTRODUCTION

As 5th Generation (5G) reaches maturity, research and standardization bodies are exploring 6th Generation (6G) use cases and evolution directions. There is a consensus that 6G networks should ensure environmental and economic sustainability [1], [2]. To meet these goals cost-effectively, 6G is expected to reuse 5G components while adding new features to deliver services and value to customers [1]. Hence, 6G should enable continuous and incremental evolution by design [2]. Yet, many proposals for the 6G Core Network (CN) design are revolutionary, contradicting the above aims.

To leverage the cloud ecosystem, mobile CN architecture requires several improvements, including inter-Network Function (NF) communication efficiency [3], lighter NFs (ready for microservice architectures) [4], or data flow organization [5]. A data-centric paradigm supports this evolution by introducing stateless NFs and reducing NF interactions to operations on data, thereby increasing flexibility and simplifying NF implementation and upgrades [5], [6]. Frequent database access and synchronization delays, however, can increase CP latency [7], which can be critical for procedures requiring prompt execution (e.g., satellite-based) and complicates database design.

Software Defined Network (SDN) is considered one of the key enablers to provide programmability in 6G mobile networks. The logical centralization and software-driven control enable optimization and advanced routing, e.g., multi-path or Content-based Routing (CBR) [8]. For today, SDN is mainly considered in the User Plane context while its potential for exploitation in CN is often overlooked.

In this paper, we introduce the Hybrid SDN-based Data-Centric Core Network (HSDCN) architecture, which extends 3GPP 5G CN with mechanisms supporting gradual evolution towards 6G. In HSDCN, we introduce SDN-driven content-based and multi-path routing capabilities for CN exchange customization, including complex NF chaining, parallelization, or support for data-centric and AI-native networks. The proposal requires minimal changes to the implementation of 3GPP NFs.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews related work, Section III describes the HSDCN concept, Section IV presents initial evaluation, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

The introduction of the 5G System (5GS) represented a major shift in mobile networks, driven by network softwarization, virtualization [9], and a non-monolithic, modular architecture based on service-based architecture (Service-Based Architecture (SBA)) and network functions (NFs) [9]. Currently, 5GS is highly complex, comprising more than 40 different NFs [9] and supporting over 500 distinct procedures [10]. Although the standardization of 6G is still in its early stages, there is a general consensus that many 5GS components will be reused, with an emphasis on achieving greater simplicity, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness [2]. The initial set of generic 6G requirements has already been defined, highlighting goals such as enhanced network integration and flexibility, AI-native design, true cloud-nativeness, and increased automation [2], [11], [12]. Additionally, new use cases have been identified for 6G [11], including scenarios like Immersive/Massive Communication and Ubiquitous Connectivity.

To address the above, several revolutionary 6G architecture visions have emerged. The key paradigms include the user-centric (per-UE) mobile networks [13], NFs decomposition into μ NFs [4], parallelizing procedure execution [3], stateless NF

and data-centric network [5], [14] or procedure-oriented networks (i.e., where End-to-End (E2E) procedures are executed by generic workers) [15]. Finally, Artificial Intelligence (AI) architectures integrating AI with 6G, such as DAEMON [16], are proposed.

Moving toward a truly cloud-native CN involves decoupling of data and its processing. It can be achieved via data-centric architectures with stateless NFs [5], [14], in which NFs execute procedures by updating User Equipment (UE)/network state data in a dedicated database, reducing complex inter-NF interactions to sequential operations on data. This lowers complexity, improves security, or enhances AI/ML models quality [14]. However, frequent database access can increase CP delay. Another challenge stems from SBA and Service Communication Proxy (SCP) [5] – a centralized CP message broker for NF clusters. SCP aggregates CP messages prior to routing, which constitutes a potential choke point for CP links and increases CP delay due to suboptimal network paths, and SCP processing overhead. Additionally, the 5G SBA is host-centric (NFs are mapped to IP locators), which limits scalability and suitability for distributed NF deployments [5].

One potential approach is to direct CP traffic simultaneously to databases and NFs by leveraging Service Function Chaining (SFC) [17] for flow processing and policy-based routing. The conventional IETF SFC architecture is protocol-agnostic and relies on unicast communication between nodes, which can restrict the flexibility of service chain configurations. To address this, various methods have been proposed to enhance SFC flexibility, such as integrating Segment Routing (SR) [18], utilizing Content-based Routing (CBR) with OpenFlow (OF) and Virtual LAN (VLAN) tagging [19], or employing P4 switches to enable a network-layer, content-based publish-subscribe mechanism [8]. Similarly, the work in [20] introduces a protocol-oblivious, CBR SDN architecture, further illustrating the suitability of SDN for content-centric networking.

Most 6G architectures are disruptive and costly. For sustainable evolution and faster monetization, 6G should iteratively upgrade 5G. We propose a CN architecture combining distributed SDN, data-centricity, and CBR to bridge these gaps.

III. HYBRID SDN-BASED DATA-CENTRIC CORE NETWORK (HSDCN)

The main goals of HSDCN are to enhance CN flexibility, facilitate iterative CN evolution and low-cost adaptation. To this end, HSDCN considers: i) support for data-centric networking; ii) CP traffic optimisation; iii) using SFCs to implement procedures to optimize CP latency; and iv) integration with AI functions and frameworks. The concept reuses 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) NFs definition [9] with minimal extensions to facilitate implementation of new services based on already implemented NFs. HSDCN comprises three inter-working parts described in the next sections (cf. Fig. 1):

- *Hierarchical Multi-controller SDN* – responsible for management and control of the CP network at the transport level. It comprises components and APIs supporting content-based and multi-path routing for CP NFs;
- *Data-centric CN* – comprising legacy 5G and 6G Intelligent NFs (INFs) – the functions with embedded AI capabilities. The NFs are either stateless or stateful instances and implement traditional REpresentational State Transfer (REST)-based interfaces for communication over SBA. Each NF/INF can implement Content-based Routing Proxy (CBRP), which is an additional interface that provides CBR capabilities in CN. The CBRP behaviour is configured directly by SDN controllers via dedicated Application Programming Interfaces (APIs);
- *Intelligence Plane (IPL) components* – comprising AI-driven functions, both generic and network-oriented ones, and database systems for centralized data storage acting as a single source of truth for network operations.

Fig. 1: Overall view of HSDCN concept

A. Hierarchical multi-controller SDN

The proposed hierarchical multi-controller (multi-domain) SDN aims to provide optimized connectivity for the signaling traffic and increase the flexibility of inter-NF exchange at scale via CBR and multi-path support (cf. Fig. 2). The framework

comprises two levels: i) *global level* – centralized Global SDNC (G-SDNC) responsible for global network control. It is assumed that G-SDNC has a limited network view, which comprises a network graph composed of NF deployment sites (e.g., data centers), domain gateways, and logical connections between them; ii) *domain level* – responsible for the control and management of domain Data Plane (DP) devices (e.g., OF switches); Due to different requirements related to spatial distribution of equipment, we consider two SDNC (domain) types: Local SDNC (L-SDNC) – LAN/MAN SDN networks, and WAN SDNC (W-SDNC) – Software-Defined Wide Area Networks interconnecting LAN/MAN domains.

Fig. 2: Content-based Routing (CBR) support in HSDCN with an E2E CBR setup procedure (steps 1-10)

Each NF can be extended with Content-based Routing Proxy (CBRP), whose role is two-fold. First, it filters outbound traffic according to configurable Content Filter (CF). This behavior can be implemented either as a proxy to the NF REST interface (scanning of outbound traffic), or within the interface implementation (a latency-efficient option). Second, it performs the packet marking by injecting unique tags into the packets that match the defined filter. The tags can be injected directly into the packet headers (e.g., DSCP/TOS fields, IPv6 extension headers) or via encapsulation (VLAN, VXLAN, etc.). The DP devices must be capable of matching on the fields to forward packets based on the tag set in packet header. Each CF is associated with a unique Flow Identification Data (FID) that comprises:

- Flow Graph (FG) – a directed graph containing NF as vertices and links symbolizing the connections representing data flow to implement (connections between NFs);
- unique tag to be associated with the flow installed in the network devices (e.g., VLAN ID), and;
- discriminatory features (primarily at Layer 7), such as, e.g., NF service types, NF service groups (e.g., authorization, authentication), NF endpoints, network events, or values within messages (configurable by operator).

At once, CBRP can run multiple CFs simultaneously. The combination of FID and CF enables the implementation of a low-overhead publish-subscribe mechanism using simple SDN routing. Moreover, the pure tag-based forwarding is enabled without the need to specify IP addresses for either the packet source or destination. As a result, this approach contributes to the cloud-nativeness of the architecture as the NF interactions are defined by the data flow between labeled NFs rather than IP source-destination pairs (diminishing the burden of IP address pools management). It must be emphasized that setting a tag-based processing does not necessitate resigning from traditional Internet Protocol (IP)-based routing. It is required, however, to reserve tag range for CBRP to avoid conflicts with other SDN forwarding rules. Finally, CBRP exposes APIs for updating its configuration. Fig. 2 shows the components responsible for E2E CBR setup along with the individual setup steps (hereafter referred to as (x)). These are:

- *CBR Front End*: the interface for programmatic configuration of CBR at global and domain levels via maps comprising a list of one or more CFs with assigned FIDs. It performs requester authorization, validates the CBR configuration, and routes requests to CBR-Cs.
- *Content-based Routing Controller (CBR-C)* SDN application responsible for enforcing the configuration of CBR for all NFs specified within FG.
- *Content-based Routing Registry (CBRR)*: registry which stores the CBR configuration, including the maps of CF and FID installed in CBRP, security policies, etc.;

The CBR is set up at the global level as follows. Upon CBR configuration request (1), its validation at Front End and authorization, the request is routed to CBR-C (2). CBR-C requests G-SDNC to calculate E2E path for the entire FG (3). The

E2E path comprises domain paths composed of compute nodes in which NFs are deployed, domain gateways, and logical links between them. G-SDNC instructs domain controllers to set up domain paths using provided logical links and nodes, with rules specified in domain FIDs (4). At the domain level SDN Controllers (SDNCs) calculate the full domain path and install entries in respective DP switches that contain matching instructions on tags and forwarding rules from FID (5). If the E2E path is set up successfully, global CBR-C splits the full FG into domain FGs based on the domain membership of NFs. Each FG is then sent with FID (discriminatory data, VLAN ID, etc.) to relevant CBR-Cs for enforcement (6) and stored in CBRR (7). After authorization and validation (8), domain CBR-Cs update CBRPs of NFs (via APIs) with CF and FID (9), thus enforcing an E2E chain (see Fig. 4). Domain CBR configuration is also stored in domain CBRRs (10). If a domain-level CBR update is requested, enforcement follows the same principles as above, except that the path is calculated and enforced by L-SDNC/W-SDNC (5). The remaining steps (8)–(10) apply unchanged.

Finally, each SDNC maintains a connection to the Intelligence Plane (IPL) via Intelligence Plane Gateways (IPGs) (see Section III-B) to store network performance metrics, e.g., link utilization, delay, and consume IPL services to optimize CN traffic. While we assume wide SDN adoption, a hybrid network with SDN and non-SDN capable domains can be exploited, provided the latter support tag-based forwarding.

B. Intelligence Plane & data-centric Core Network (CN)

We extend the 5G CN with components supporting Intelligence Plane (IPL), data-centricity, AI-driven operations, and CBR (cf. Fig. 3). The IPL is a vertical plane spanning all other network planes, aggregating AI-based functions across layers and providing logically centralized data storage and exposure.

Fig. 3: Data-centric enabled CN and interactions with IPL

It comprises:

- *Intelligent NF (INF)*: a generic function embedding cognitive capabilities. INF can be either the 3GPP NF with embedded AI model (i.e., native-AI NF) or a generic engine implementing an AI/ML algorithm and exposing AI services to external consumers (e.g., analytics).
- *Intelligence Plane Gateway (IPG)*: the entrypoint to the IPL service mesh, providing service discovery capabilities for NF and INF and access control;
- *Core Network Database (NDB)*: a physically distributed, logically centralized database (data lake) storing network/user state and context, with synchronized system-wide access. By design, Core Network Database (NDB) instances should be collocated, with CN functions for high-availability. As the storage functionality will span multiple network domains, the NDB should employ data retention, replication, and synchronization mechanisms to maintain a globally consistent network state information;

Each IPL component can communicate either over the IPL message bus (publish/subscribe) or using CBR. Regarding data-centric core, we consider both stateless and legacy stateful NFs. The foremost utilize NDB services (accessed via IPG) to store, collect, and update state data during procedure execution. For legacy NFs, additional mechanisms for replicating data stored within 5G NFs should be adopted (e.g., UDM, UDR, or NRF content mirroring) to maintain state consistency.

For state definition in NDB, the compromise strategy should be adopted [14] that proposes user and NF type granularity – one state for each user dedicated to a specific network function type. The state can be stored by NFs at the message level (state created at the procedure start and consecutive updates), transaction level (state created after each transaction), or procedure level (state created after all transactions are executed) [14]. A message-level approach minimizes latency impact during operation and facilitates faster failure recovery. Hence, every time the CN procedure is executed, the respective state information for the UE/NF is created/updated in NDB.

To maximize economic savings, 3GPP NF REST interfaces can be extended with CBRP (cf. Section III-A) to configure tags associated for specific message contents or NF services/group (e.g., security, authentication), enabling fine-grained CP messages routing. Moreover, we introduce Content-based Routing Support Function (CRSF) (a type of Application Function (AF)), which extends the role of SCP in terms of service discovery and additionally serves as the interconnect point between NFs and CBR applications. It enables NFs to request service subscriptions via content-based delivery without direct exchange with the NF.

CBR and multipath routing enable the implementation of SFCs (cf. Fig. 4). NFs can be chained to support signaling branching—e.g., parallel procedure execution or optimized NDB state updates by distributing traffic to relevant NFs and the NDB. The HSDCN framework also removes the need for NFs to store subscriber information, as this is maintained in the CBRR, reducing coupling between instances. Moreover, CBR-based SFC is well suited for dynamic topologies such as Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN), where paths can be prepared and adjusted in advance, enabling proactive, minimal NF reconfiguration and reducing costly CP signaling

Finally, although the HSDCN framework provides basic security mechanisms (e.g., authorization and access control via IPG and CBR front ends), further hardening is essential. This includes, e.g., adopting zero-trust mechanisms, blockchain-based state storage in the NDB, or leveraging SDN security applications. In addition, SDN-specific attack vectors—such as controller vulnerabilities, CP saturation, message spoofing, or DP flooding—must be analyzed and mitigated through measures like security SDN applications or SDNC redundancy.

Fig. 4: Overview of SFC in distributed SDN network

IV. EVALUATION

To maintain scalability, network operators usually deploy the core network with SCP as an NFs mediator (i.e., a star topology) to offload NRF [5]. Hereby, we conduct initial simulations to evaluate the impact of propagation delay between the NF of SCP-based and HSDCN deployment options. We consider two metrics: total transmission latency τ_t (a sum of delays per procedure step τ_n) and total number of packet hops in the NF chain (corresponding to the consumed bandwidth):

$$\tau_t = \sum_n^N \tau_n \quad (1)$$

$$p_t = \sum_n^N |p_n| \quad (2)$$

where, p_n is the length of a path in hops between two NFs. For SCP variant (τ^{SCP}) each message between two NFs is transferred via SCP node w_{SCP} , whereas HSDCN (τ^{HSDCN}) sends the message directly to the NF. For NFs u and v the packet delay can be expressed as:

$$\tau_n^{SCP}(u, v) = \tau(u, w_{SCP}) + \tau(w_{SCP}, v) + \tau_p \quad (3)$$

$$\tau_n^{HSDCN} = \tau(u, v) + \tau_0 + \tau_p \quad (4)$$

, where τ_p – processing delay at switch (queuing, header matching, etc.), and τ_0 – overhead specific to CBRP induced by packet parsing and injection of tags into the packet headers.

To estimate the potential performance gains, we generated 2,500 random graphs (fat tree-like topologies) with node numbers varying from 20 to 50 nodes, corresponding to cloud, regional, and edge compute nodes, distributed uniformly over areas spanning a radius of 50 to 250 km. For link latency computation, we assumed propagation speed as in fiber (refractive index $\eta \approx 1.44$). Then, we perform NF placement (5–10 NFs) over the graph nodes, while minimizing the latency between NFs. Finally, we define NF chains composed of 5 to 20 NFs that correspond to the execution of a network procedure. Fig. 5 shows the outcome of total latency and hop count for SCP-based and HSDCN deployments. We assume $\tau_0 \leq 1$ ms.

HSDCN offers significant improvements in both delay and bandwidth efficiency. Specifically, it achieves an average reduction of 26% in latency (τ_t) and a 19% decrease in total path length (p_t), resulting in substantial bandwidth savings during E2E

Fig. 5: Performance gains of HSDCN over SCP-based deployment: latency (a, b) and path length (c, d). Panels (b) and (d) show differences relative to the deployment-area size.

procedure execution. These benefits become more pronounced as the distance between compute nodes hosting the NFs increases, since routing through a centralized SCP introduces greater propagation delays. Additionally, HSDCN demonstrates a smaller inter-quartile range for both τ_t and p_t , highlighting its suitability for time-sensitive applications such as NTN systems. Another advantage is that HSDCN can easily avoid traffic concentration points, a challenge in SCP-based deployments that often necessitates additional SCP instances, further network disaggregation, and increased overhead. However, these advantages come with the trade-off of added configuration overhead for CBRP and a larger deployment footprint for HSDCN (including SDN components, CBR applications, CRSF, and IPL functions). The precise impact of these factors has yet to be evaluated and warrants further investigation.

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes Hybrid SDN-based Data-Centric Core Network (HSDCN), bridging the gap between 5G and emerging 6G architectures. HSDCN combines 3GPP CN with a data-centric paradigm and hierarchical multi-domain SDN to enable incremental CN evolution. It introduces content-based and multi-path routing for CP traffic to enhance CN flexibility, support dynamic complex SFC, facilitate signaling branching, and optimize NFs exchange. HSDCN also offers a scalable alternative for mesh CN deployments. Initial simulations show 26% lower latency with CBR versus SCP-based CNs. Future work will focus on security extensions, implementation in the emulation environment, and evaluation of CP performance compared to 3GPP deployment models.

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